

GENETIC INHERITANCE AND VARIABILITY OF MAIN STEM HEIGHT IN F1 HYBRIDS OF GOSSYPIUM HIRSUTUM L. UNDER OPTIMAL AND WATER- DEFICIT CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

*In this study, one of the synthetic selection methods — biparental hybridization — was used to improve drought tolerance in varieties and lines belonging to *Gossypium hirsutum* L. The inheritance and variability of the morphological trait "main stem height" in F1 hybrids obtained through biparental crosses were studied under both optimal irrigation and water-deficit conditions. The results showed that under optimal irrigation, certain maternal genotypes (Saenr-Pena-85, Catamarca-811) and paternal genotypes (C-6580) exhibited higher stem height values compared to the standard variety (C-6524). Among the F1 hybrids, no combinations exceeded their parental forms in terms of stem height. However, under water-deficit conditions, some hybrids (e.g., F1 C-6580 × Saenr Pena-85, F1 C-6580 × Acala-40) demonstrated superior performance compared to both parents. Analysis of the dominance index (hp) revealed incomplete dominance, negative and positive heterosis among the F1 combinations. Particularly, the hybrids F1 Sulton × Saenr Pena-85, F1 Sulton × Hapicala-19, F1 C-6580 × Acala-40, and F1 Nam-77 × Acala-40 showed positive heterosis, indicating their potential for further selection and breeding programs.*

Introduction: Global climate change, particularly challenges such as drought and water scarcity, has a significant negative impact on the growth and productivity of agricultural crops, including cotton. Therefore, the development of drought-tolerant and stable-yielding varieties has become one of the urgent tasks in modern breeding programs [1;2.]. Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) is a leading crop in the textile industry, and in-depth study of its morphological traits is essential for improving the efficiency of selection processes [3.]. Among these traits, main stem height plays an important role in determining yield potential, suitability for mechanized harvesting, and adaptability to agrotechnical practices. This trait is strongly influenced by both genetic factors and environmental conditions, particularly

irrigation regimes. Thus, studying the inheritance patterns of stem height, including the manifestation of heterosis under water-deficit conditions, is of great importance in breeding programs. In this study, the inheritance and variability of main stem height were evaluated in F₁ hybrids obtained through biparental crosses among varieties and lines of *G. hirsutum* L. under two environmental conditions: optimal irrigation and water-deficit stress. Genetic parameters such as dominance index (hp) and coefficient of variation (V%) were used to assess the trait's heritability and heterosis expression. The results of this study contribute to identifying promising hybrid combinations for the development of drought-tolerant cotton varieties.

Materials and Methods. Field experiments were conducted at the experimental field of Tashkent State Agrarian University. The research materials included local and foreign varieties and lines of *Gossypium hirsutum* L., such as Sulton, C-6580, Namangan-77, Saenr-Pena-85, Acala-40, Hapicala-19, and Catamarca 811. F₁ hybrids obtained through biparental crosses among these genotypes were also included in the study. The variety C-6524 was used as the standard (control) cultivar. Agrotechnical practices were carried out in accordance with the guidelines developed and approved by the Uzbek Scientific Research Institute of Cotton Breeding and Seed Production (UzPITI) [6]. In the field, seeds were sown using a 60×20–1 cm planting scheme, at a depth of 3–4 cm, with 3 to 4 seeds per hill. Experimental variants were arranged in three replications using a randomized complete block design. The experimental data were statistically analyzed following the methodology of B.A. Dospekhov [5].

Results and Discussion. In this study, one of the synthetic selection methods — biparental hybridization — was employed to improve drought tolerance in varieties and genotypes of *Gossypium hirsutum* L. Among the morphological traits, the main stem height of the F₁ hybrids derived from biparental crosses was analyzed in comparison with their respective parents and the standard variety (C-6524). Field experiments were conducted under two different environmental conditions: optimal irrigation and water-deficit stress. In both environments, data collected from the parental lines and F₁ hybrid combinations were statistically analyzed. It is well established that in cotton, the main stem height should ideally range between 100–120 cm, and the plant should exhibit a compact, non-branching growth habit. This trait significantly influences yield potential and facilitates mechanical harvesting. During the early growth stage (20–30 days after emergence), stem height typically ranges from 10–20 cm. As the vegetative phase progresses, it reaches approximately 70 cm. At the flowering and boll-setting stages, the main stem height may reach 100–120 cm, and in some tetraploid cultivars, up to 150 cm. This trait is influenced by genetic characteristics of the cultivar, agrotechnical practices, and the prevailing soil-climatic conditions.

Under optimal growing conditions, the inheritance and variability of main stem height were analyzed in parental lines and their F₁ hybrids. According to average values, the highest results for this trait were observed in the maternal lines Saenr-Pena-85 (M = 118.27 cm) and Catamarca-811 (M = 112.05 cm), while among the paternal lines, C-6580 showed the highest mean (M = 110.64 cm), all of which outperformed the standard variety C-6524. Among the F₁ hybrids, no combinations exceeded their parental lines in terms of stem height. However, the highest results among hybrids were recorded in F₁ C-6580 × Saenr-Pena-85 (M = 115.36 cm)

and F₁ Nam-77 × Saenr-Pena-85 (M = 115.45 cm), while the lowest stem height was observed in F₁ Sulton × Acala-40 (M = 95.46 cm) (see Table 1). The coefficient of variation (V%) for this trait ranged from 3.67% to 14.40% across the parental forms and F₁ combinations. Analysis of the dominance index (hp) revealed that, out of 12 F₁ hybrid combinations, 7 exhibited incomplete partial dominance (0 < hp < 1), 1 showed no dominance (hp = 0), and 4 combinations (F₁ Sulton × Hapicala-19, F₁ C-6577 × 4017, F₁ C-6580 × Catamarca-811, F₁ Nam-77 × Hapicala-19, F₁ Nam-77 × Catamarca-811) displayed various degrees of heterosis (hp = 1). These heterotic combinations are considered promising for further breeding programs. Under water-deficit conditions (irrigation scheme 0:1:0), the inheritance and variability of main stem height were also evaluated. In these conditions, the highest average values were recorded in the maternal genotypes Saenr-Pena-85 (M = 90.95 cm) and Catamarca-811 (M = 90.76 cm), as well as the paternal line C-6580 (M = 90.12 cm). Among the F₁ hybrids, certain combinations outperformed their parents, including F₁ C-6580 × Saenr-Pena-85 (M = 93.67 cm) and F₁ C-6580 × Acala-40 (M = 93.0 cm). On the other hand, the lowest values were noted in F₁ C-6580 × Catamarca-811 (M = 75.54 cm) and F₁ C-6580 × Hapicala-19 (M = 78.07 cm).

Table 1

№	Names of the standard variety, parental lines, and F ₁ hybrid combinations	Height of the main stem, (sm)					
		Optimal irrigation conditions			Water deficit conditions		
		M±m	V%	hp	M±m	V%	hp
1	S-6524 (St)	100,54±1,05	11,02		90,43±1,45	13,63	
2	Sulton	95,85±1,12	8,97		85,28±1,02	18,45	
3	C-6580	110,64±0,99	14,35		90,12±0,76	14,33	
4	Namangan-77	105,10±2,02	8,54		82,18±1,56	22,06	
5	Saenr-Pena-85	118,27±0,59	12,38		90,95±0,93	11,78	
6	Acala-40	95,50±1,32	8,74		80,08±1,36	24,68	
7	Hapicala-19	104,72±2,12	13,40		80,47±2,24	23,40	
8	Catamarca 811	112,05±1,80	10,22		90,76±0,75	11,98	
9	Sulton x Saenr Pena-85	110,65±1,41	10,86	0,66	93,67±1,02	9,67	1,96
10	Sulton x Acala-40	95,46±0,78	9,05	-0,11	81,37±0,88	12,08	-0,50
11	Sulton x Hapicala-19	108,00±1,14	13,23	1,37	92,00±0,85	8,76	3,79
12	Sulton x Catamarca 811	110,24±0,65	6,67	0,89	90,34±0,99	16,34	0,85
13	C-6580 x Saenr Pena-85	115,36±1,18	14,40	0,62	85,60±0,64	13,44	11,89
14	C-6580 x Acala-40	100,47±1,34	5,54	0,33	93,00±1,45	10,87	1,57
15	C-6580x Hapicala-19	105,46±0,87	8,61	0,13	78,07±0,87	25,09	-1,50
16	C-6580 x Catamarca 811	112,60±0,98	7,15	1,00	75,54±0,72	27,13	-46,56
17	Nam-77 x Saenr Pena-85	115,45±1,30	3,67	0,79	82,41±1,15	10,15	-0,95
18	Nam-77 x Acala-40	105,89±1,22	10,28	0,75	85,45±1,42	13,36	4,11
19	Nam-77 x Hapicala-19	110,76±1,08	11,36	1,00	80,57±0,99	14,47	-0,88
20	Nam-77 x Catamarca 811	115,24±1,04	5,12	1,00	85,94±0,98	15,36	-0,12

Heritability of main stem height trait under optimal irrigation and drought conditions in the standard variety, parental lines, and F₁ hybrid combinations.

The coefficient of variation (V%) ranged from 8.76% to 27.13% among the initial material and hybrid combinations. The dominance index (hp) values presented in table 1 indicate that among the 12 F₁ hybrid combinations, heritability was observed in cases of negative heterosis, positive heterosis, and incomplete dominance. Accordingly, it is important to consider the hybrid combinations exhibiting positive heterosis (F₁ Sulton x Saenr Pena-85, F₁ Sulton x Hapicala-19, F₁ C-6580 x Acala-40, F₁ Nam-77 x Acala-40) in subsequent selection experiments.

Conclusion: Based on the analyzed data, the following conclusions were drawn:

The main stem height trait in *G. hirsutum* L. cotton varieties is strongly influenced by agro-technical conditions and genetic factors. The heritability of main stem height in F₁ progenies obtained through hybridization exhibited various types of dominance (incomplete dominance, heterosis, and negative heterosis). Under drought conditions, some F₁ combinations demonstrated positive heterosis, and these hybrids (F₁ Sulton x Saenr Pena-85, F₁ Sulton x Hapicala-19, F₁ C-6580 x Acala-40, F₁ Nam-77 x Acala-40) can be valuable sources for further selection breeding. The wide range of variation coefficients (8.76–27.13%) provides a high potential for selection based on main stem height.

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